

Research

Mitigating Crossing Risks: A Study of Pedestrian Behavior in Anambra State, Nigeria: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to mitigate the probability of pedestrian accidents in Anambra State, Nigeria, by analyzing pedestrian behaviour using structural equation modelling (SEM). The data on demographics, perceived behavioural control in crossing scenarios, subjective norms, attitudes towards traffic safety, and behavioural intents were gathered using a standardized questionnaire. A total of 243 individuals 123 men (50.6%) and 120 women (49.4%) completed the online survey. The majority of respondents (91.4%) were between the ages of 19 and 35.

The results reveal that while attitude did not significantly predict behavioral intentions, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control played crucial roles, with p-values of 0.004 and 0.001, respectively. This underscores the importance of considering social influences and perceived control in shaping pedestrian behavior. Notably, demographic characteristics did not show significance in this study.

The study also highlights the necessity of customized interventions based on socioeconomic factors and infrastructure modifications in order to enhance pedestrian safety. Technology improvements and educational initiatives based on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) are suggested as useful tactics to lower the risks associated with road-crossing.

Keywords: Pedestrian behaviour; pedestrian safety; structural equation modelling; Confirmatory factor analysis.

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Introduction

Today, pedestrians make up the majority of all road users. Among all users of the road, pedestrians are one of the most at risk [1, 2]. Over 50% of traffic-related injuries and fatalities in developing nations, including Nigeria, happens to pedestrians [3]. Now recent researchers have found out that road traffic accidents (RTAs) have also been demonstrated in studies to be a significant source of serious injuries and dead in pedestrians worldwide, with developing nations accounting for a disproportionate amount of these incidents [4]. More than 1.2 million pedestrians die from road traffic accidents yearly, ranking (RTA) the eighth most frequent cause of death in the world for all age groups [5]. For instance, in Nigeria, understanding street crossing behaviors of the young people becomes crucial, where people aged 24 and below make up 64% of the population, for a number of reasons. First, pedestrians are at risk for accidents since many

cities lack pedestrian sidewalks, have insufficient zebra crossing locations, and lack traffic control officials on important roadways. Secondly, it has been discovered that in various areas of the nation, the highest populations of patients with trauma caused by traffic accidents are students (17.5%) and young traders (14.7%) [6]. Thirdly, studies have revealed that both motorists and pedestrians frequently disobey traffic laws in the nation, which makes it even more likely that pedestrians may be hurt in car accidents [7].

In addition, according to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), 93% of traffic deaths globally take place in low- and middle-income nations (LMIC), also the World Health Organization (WHO) reports that the risk of road traffic accident is highest in the African continent, where 26.6/100,000 people dwell. Despite deliberate attempts to lower the number of pedestrian accidents, Nigeria, one of the African nations, remains among the most seriously afflicted. The author goes on to explain that the country has suffered significant losses as a result of fatal automotive accidents, citing the nearly 194,000 km of total road length, approximately 167 million people living in the country, an estimated 7.6 million vehicles, and 34,120 km of federal, 30,500 km of state, and 129,580 km of local roads [8]. Understanding how pedestrians engage with the roadway and the traffic environment may be gained by analyzing the crossing behaviour of people in urban area like in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Understanding how they adhere to current traffic regulations while striking a balance between comfort and safety at the cost of delay can also be helpful. The behaviour of pedestrians crossing the street has been the subject of several research. For example, research has indicated in certain publications that socioeconomic considerations have an impact on how people cross the street [9, 10].

In addition, in south-west Nigeria, Olawole and Olayiwola [11] observed how pedestrians behaved when approaching, at, and crossing the roadway. There are many studies on exploring the behaviour of pedestrians crossing the road in developed countries but very scanty in low- and middle-income nations (LMIC) like Nigeria, for instance, the Chinese pedestrians' intentions to cross the road in two distinct road crossing circumstances (non-conformity and conformity) were examined by Zhou et al. [12] using data on age, gender, and conformity propensity. The study found that people were more likely to cross the street when other people were doing the same thing. It used a sample of 426 respondents who responded to two sets of questionnaires: a demographic questionnaire and another questionnaire based on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). Greater social conformity inclinations were correlated with increased intent to cross the road in both circumstances compared to lower conformity tendencies. The non-conformity and conformity scenarios' respective variances were both 36% and 48% explained by the model. The shared factors for both circumstances were attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control, and perceived risk. Further research carried out by Lennon et al., [13] in Australia examined pedestrian self-reported usage of smart phones and revealed that TPB components explained almost 55% of the variation in behavioural intention to participate in distracted street-crossing among young adults aged 18–30 years. The two predictors that emerged were subjective norm and attitude towards the behaviour, with attitude towards the behaviour being the most significant predictor. Additionally, the TPB has been used to analyze pedestrian crossing decision-making in the UK and Chile [14-16]. For instance, in three dangerous situations crossing a dual highway, a pelican crossing, and a residential street Evans and Norman [15] looked at the intentions of adults (aged 17 to 75) to cross roads. According to the study's findings, three elements of TPB (attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control) explained 37%–49% of the variance in road-crossing intentions, with perceived behavioural control appearing as the key predictive variable. The TPB has been used to evaluate a range of pedestrian intents and behaviour during the past 20 years. A portion of these research focus on violations and distraction (e.g Zhou, Romero, & Qin, 2016[17]) walking when intoxicated (Haque et al., 2012[18]), and distracted walking (Barton, Kologi, & Siron, 2016[19]), in various countries such as UK (Evans & Norman, 1998[15]), Spain (Moyano-Díaz, 2002[20]), and China (Zhou, Horrey, & Yu, 2009[12]).

The majority of research on pedestrian behavior focuses on pedestrian who violate traffic laws and distraction. In Nigeria, the majority of pedestrians cross the street without using crosswalks, which makes it difficult for drivers to

maneuver their vehicles. In addition, most pedestrian behavior while crossing the street has lately been made illegal on most road in the country has lack of road signs. Unfortunately, not much research has been done to determine pedestrian's behavior when distracted in Nigeria. There is still much to learn about this conduct. The study focuses on mitigating crossing risk in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Research framework

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) serves as a foundational framework for understanding and predicting human behavior, particularly in the context of pedestrian actions and road-crossing practices. TPB integrates key components such as attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control to forecast intentions and behaviors related to safe crossing behavior [21]. However, the application of TPB in the realm of pedestrian safety necessitates an expanded understanding that incorporates demographic variables and employs advanced analytical techniques such as structural equation modeling (SEM).

In this study, we build upon the TPB framework by incorporating demographic variables and utilizing SEM to comprehensively examine the factors influencing pedestrian behavior and intentions regarding safe road-crossing practices in Anambra State, Nigeria. Our hypotheses are formulated based on this extended TPB model:

Hypothesis

H1: Attitudes towards safe crossing behavior will positively predict pedestrian behavioral intentions to adhere to safe road-crossing practices. This hypothesis is grounded in the notion that individuals' attitudes towards pedestrian safety significantly influence their intentions and behaviors when crossing roads.

H2: Subjective norms, encompassing social influences and perceptions regarding road-crossing behavior, will positively influence pedestrian behavioral intentions to follow safe crossing practices. This hypothesis acknowledges the impact of social factors and normative beliefs on individuals' intentions to engage in safe road-crossing behavior.

H3: Perceived behavioral control, reflecting individuals' perceived ease or difficulty in crossing roads safely, will positively predict pedestrian behavioral intentions to engage in safe road-crossing behavior. This hypothesis underscores the importance of individuals' perceived ability to control their actions and navigate road-crossing situations safely.

H4: Pedestrian demographic variables, including age and gender, will significantly influence pedestrian behavioral intentions regarding safe road-crossing practices in Anambra State, Nigeria. This hypothesis recognizes the potential influence of demographic factors on individuals' intentions and behaviors related to road-crossing safety, reflecting the diverse socio-cultural context of the study area.

By examining these hypotheses within the framework of TPB and employing advanced analytical techniques, we aim to provide valuable insights into the determinants of pedestrian behavior and contribute to the development of effective strategies for enhancing pedestrian safety in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Study design

The present study used an online questionnaire survey to collect data from the study area through social media like, WhatsApp, Telegram and Facebook and also, we sent some of the questionnaire to emails addresses that we got from people that was not using social media. In addition, the questionnaire came in two sections and took approximately 10 minutes to complete. The first section was designed to evaluate demographic variables such as age and gender. The second section was designed based on behaviour TPB to evaluate attitude (3 items), subjective norms (3 items),

perceived behavioural control (3 items) and behavioural intention (3 items). All items were scored using 5-point Likert Scale. Attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and behavioural intention items were all scored from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree'.

Data analysis

A type of structural equation modelling called confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was adopted using AMOS software, the (CFA) focuses only on models for measurement. It looks at the relationships between latent variables or factors and observable measurements or indicators (such as test items, test scores, and behavioural observation ratings). The goal of latent variable measurement models, also known as factor analysis, is to determine the quantity and kind of factors that account for variance and co-variation within a set of indicators. In social science research, confirmatory factor analysis is frequently utilised. Measurement invariance analysis, concept validation, identifying method effects, and psychometric evaluation are just a few of the uses for CFA. While developing a scale, the most popular use of CFA is to look into the hidden structure of a test instrument [22]. Furthermore, Confirmation or validation of the proposed links between the factors or latent constructs and the measured variables is the main goal of CFA. This assessment determines how closely the observed variables match the theoretical structures that they are meant to quantify.

Essential elements and ideas pertaining to CFA

Latent Variables: Researchers try to quantify these unobservable entities or elements indirectly using observed variables. If these latent variables match the observed data, CFA can assist confirm it.

Indicator variables: are measurable variables that are thought to reflect the underlying latent structures. They are often referred to as manifest variables or observable variables. The correlation between these indicators and the latent variables they are intended to measure is investigated via CFA.

Model Fit Indices: Using a variety of fit indices, including the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Comparative Fit Index (CFI), CFA evaluates the fit between the suggested measurement model and the observed data. How well the suggested model matches the real data is determined by these indexes.

Results and discussion

Descriptive statistics

A total of 243 respondents a mix of men and women completed the survey. According to the survey's results, 123 (50.6%) of the respondents were men and 120 (49.4%) were women. 222 (91.4%) individuals are in the 19–35 age group, 12 (4.9%) are in the 36–55 age group, and none are in the 56–and-over age group. Of the participants, 9 (3.7%) are in the 0–18 age group. In the other hand.

Reliability and Validity Measures

The composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients ≥ 0.60 and 0.70 respectively for all the measurement scales. The discriminant validity (DV) was established as the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) as shown in Table 1, was greater than the correlations of the latent variables in the CFA [23].

Table 1: model validity measures

ITEM	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	AT	SN	PBC	BI
AT	0.826	0.613	0.075	0.832	0.783			
SN	0.753	0.516	0.075	0.824	0.274**	0.719		
PBC	0.752	0.507	0.070	0.783	-0.077	-0.016	0.712	
BI	0.763	0.539	0.070	0.844	-0.058	0.141†	0.265**	0.734

Measurement Thresholds

As shown in Table 2, all the measurement scales were subjected to confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) based on the following thresholds: Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)>0.95; r/df 3.0; standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR) ≤0.08, and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) ≤ 0.06[23].

Table 2: Model fit measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	62.772	--	--
DF	48.000	--	--
CMIN/DF	1.308	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.983	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.047	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.036	<0.06	Excellent
TLI	0.977	>0.95	Excellent
IFI	0.983	>0.95	Excellent

Attitude (AT)

This construct was measured by three item scenarios, which one of them is: “I commonly cross the road in a traffic gap because it is less distance” that is Crossing the road (Save time), rated on a 5-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5) the same as the rest. Internal consistency was strong, with a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.85.

Subjective norm (SN)

Similar to attitude, subjective norm was also measured on a 5-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). Three items were used in this construct, “My parents would agree if I cross the street safely”. The Cronbach’s alpha measured was 0.73.

Perceived behavioural control (PBC)

PBC was assessed by three items, one of the items was: “I am confident that I never use my phone while crossing the street”. The Cronbach’s alpha measured was 0.75.

Behavioural intention (BI)

This construct was measured by three items. One of the questions was: “In the near future, when crossing the road, I would expect not to be involved in any kind of road distraction, such as pressing my phone or talking with my friends”, rated on a 5-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The Cronbach’s alpha result was 0.73.

Table 3: Regression weight

Item	Direction	Item	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
AT	Towards	BI	-0.087	0.097	-.904	0.366
SN	Towards	BI	0.194	0.094	2.057	0.040
PBC	Towards	BI	0.414	0.130	3.185	0.001
Age group	Towards	BI	0.180	0.334	.540	0.589
Gender	Towards	BI	0.204	0.196	1.041	0.298

Results and Narration

This study aimed to mitigate crossing risk and by using structural equation model to assess the relationship between constructs. The results demonstrated the significant influence that perceived behavioural control (PBC) and subjective standards have on people's decisions to cross streets as shown in Table 3. Interestingly, Attitude had less influence over behavioural intentions than subjective norms, which reflect the influence of friends and family. It is implied by this emphasis on social dynamics that people's decisions about how to cross the street are more influenced by outside factors than by internal ideas. Moreover, a significant factor over subjective norms and attitude was shown to be perceived behavioural control (PBC). Remarkably, attitudes by themselves did not substantially impact behavioural intentions, in contrast to TPB expectations. This may be explained by differences in educational influences on road safety behaviour, infrastructure, and cultural standards. It's interesting to note that neither age or gender were significant to behavioural intentions. These results demonstrate the complex interactions among individual convictions, and social influences suggesting that while demographic characteristics and attitude may not have a significant impact on pedestrian behaviour, social contexts are important determinants of intention.

Conclusions

These results highlight the complex relationships that exist between individual beliefs and social factors. Although demographic and personal attitudes may not have much of an impact, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms were found to be crucial in determining behavioural intention. In order to improve pedestrian safety at street

crossings, this study provides policymakers and road safety authorities with useful guidance for creating more successful interventions that center on social effects and road familiarity.

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